

Grain quality characteristics of aromatic and nonaromatic rice cultivars

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Milled rice is judged by its appearance, which depends on grain size and shape, whiteness, and translucency. Broken and unattractive grains diminish the economic value of rice that is consumed as whole grain. Rice consumers want products with the best qualities. Selection for quality characters therefore leads to varieties more readily accepted by farmers and consum-

ers. We therefore aimed to develop high-yielding varieties with these grain quality characteristics—long slender or medium-long slender translucent grain with high milling recovery, intermediate gelatinization temperature (GT), and very good grain elongation. Grain elongation is a special characteristic of several high-grain-quality varieties such as Basmati 370 and

Nga Kywe. This polygenically controlled trait is difficult to transfer.

In the wet season (June to September), we evaluated 12 high-yielding varieties, 11 IET (Initial Evaluation Trial) lines, and scented rice for hulling, milling, head rice recovery, and quality parameters such as amylose content (AC) and gel consistency (GC) (see table). Each genotype was

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Genotype	% total milled rice	Head rice recovery (%)	Kernel length (mm)	Kernel width (mm)	Length/breadth ratio	Linear elongation ratio	Alkali spreading value	Gelatinization temp. ^a	Amylose content (%)	Type	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
<i>High-yielding varieties</i>											
ADT36	64.4	44.2	6.7	1.9	3.5	1.8	3.3	I	28.4	Hard	5.0
ADT42	73.2	44.3	6.6	1.9	3.5	1.8	3.7	I	27.3	Hard	6.0
ADT43	62.7	44.7	5.7	2.3	2.4	1.6	6.8	L	26.2	Hard	5.9
ADRH1	69.5	36.6	6.8	2.2	3.1	1.7	3.8	I	24.3	Hard	6.4
CORH1	72.2	43.0	5.6	2.3	2.4	1.6	7.0	L	25.1	Hard	6.0
ASD16	70.7	44.5	5.2	2.7	1.9	1.5	7.0	L	24.3	Hard	5.6
ASD17	70.6	48.1	5.4	2.8	1.9	1.4	6.9	L	28.1	Hard	5.4
ASD20	64.6	50.5	6.8	2.0	3.4	1.7	3.8	I	27.3	Hard	6.7
TKM9	71.9	45.4	5.7	2.6	2.2	1.2	6.6	L	30.4	Hard	6.0
MDU5	72.6	49.1	5.8	2.5	2.4	1.5	7.0	L	26.3	Hard	4.9
IR50	72.5	51.1	6.7	2.0	3.5	1.7	3.2	I	23.1	Hard	6.0
IR64	68.9	42.5	6.8	1.9	3.6	1.8	3.6	I	21.3	Hard	5.8
<i>IET lines^b</i>											
JGL496	68.6	46.4	5.5	1.6	3.4	1.4	6.0	L	21.3	Hard	6.0
CB96073	72.5	44.6	5.6	1.5	3.6	1.3	6.0	L	26.4	Hard	6.2
CB(DH)95299	66.0	42.7	5.0	1.3	3.8	1.6	7.0	L	24.7	Hard	5.4
MTU1029	74.2	51.3	5.6	1.6	3.5	1.6	6.4	L	23.1	Hard	5.2
HKR95-219	70.6	44.6	6.7	2.0	3.4	1.7	3.5	I	22.3	Hard	5.6
CSR27	70.7	50.4	6.6	3.3	2.0	1.4	6.4	L	21.8	Hard	5.3
NWGR9	72.3	46.0	6.8	2.0	3.4	1.7	3.6	I	24.4	Hard	5.2
NWGR13	71.0	43.8	6.8	2.0	3.4	1.7	3.9	I	20.0	Hard	5.7
RR380-10-3	75.6	32.1	6.6	3.6	1.8	1.6	3.6	I	24.3	Hard	5.6
RR389-8-2	68.6	36.6	6.6	1.9	3.4	1.5	7.0	L	26.1	Hard	5.3
RNRM 22	62.3	33.9	6.8	3.3	2.0	1.3	3.5	I	23.7	Hard	5.8
Basmati 370 ^c	60.3	49.6	7.0	2.1	3.2	1.8	3.3	I	19.2	Medium	3.9
Basmati 385 ^c	64.5	31.1	6.8	2.2	3.1	1.5	3.7	I	19.3	Medium	4.0
Pusa Basmat 1 ^c	62.4	44.4	7.0	2.1	3.2	1.8	3.2	I	19.6	Medium	4.3
Kasturi ^c	63.4	38.9	5.7	2.4	2.3	1.5	7.0	L	19.9	Medium	4.2
Pak. Basmati ^c	61.2	46.6	6.9	2.3	2.8	1.5	3.4	I	21.3	Medium	4.1
Har. Basmati ^c	58.7	36.6	6.7	2.1	3.1	1.7	3.2	I	20.4	Medium	4.0
Meenambur Local	77.1	39.9	4.1	1.5	2.6	1.4	7.0	L	22.3	Hard	3.0
Jeeragasamba	67.4	45.5	4.2	1.5	2.7	1.4	6.8	L	24.1	Hard	3.9
Nepaljeeragas Amba	63.4	32.3	4.0	1.5	2.6	1.4	6.7	L	23.1	Hard	3.7
White ponni	63.2	48.8	5.7	2.4	2.3	0.4	7.0	L	22.4	Hard	5.0
TM95005	72.1	49.9	5.7	2.2	2.5	1.5	7.2	L	26.5	Hard	5.4
ACM 95132	70.2	34.5	5.6	2.3	2.3	1.5	7.0	L	28.1	Hard	5.9
Mean	68.3	43.2	5.8	2.2	2.9	1.5	5.3		23.9		5.2
SE	3.76	4.88	0.75	0.43	0.51	0.07	1.57		1.5		0.77

^aL = low, I = intermediate. ^bIET = Initial Evaluation Trial. ^cAromatic rice.

transplanted in a randomized block design with three replications at 20×15-cm spacing. Observations from 10 randomly selected plants per replication in each genotype were recorded. Aroma was determined by using chopped leaves collected at 50% flowering stage.

GT is a measure of cooking ease and is indexed by the alkali digestibility test (Little et al 1958). It is measured by the alkali spreading value (ASV) of individual milled rice soaked in 1.7% KOH solution for 23 h at 30 °C using a 1–7 scale. A high rating indicates more disintegration and is classified under low GT. Rice varieties with intermediate GT (ASV of 3–5) are usually preferred over those with low GT (ASV of 6–7). The AC determines cooking behavior and eating quality of cooked rice. This was estimated and classified using a modi-

fication of Shen's method (1990), which was developed at the Cuttack Rice Research Institute (Swain and Nagaraju 1997). The GC test is a reliable index for cooked rice texture. A method modified by Cagampang (1973) was used to analyze the GC of 35 varieties. Length is classified as hard (6–10 mm), medium (11–20 mm), and soft (>20 mm).

Milled rice percentage was high for ADT42 (high-yielding variety RR380-10-3 (IET line), and Meenambur Local (scented rice). Percent head rice recovery was highest in IR50, TM95005, (MTU1029), and CSR27. ADT36 had the highest linear elongation among all genotypes. All scented varieties had intermediate (17–22%) AC and medium (11–20 mm) GC (data not shown), while the high-yielding, nonscented, and IET lines recorded higher

(>22%) AC and hard (6–10 mm) GC (data not shown). ADT36, ADRH1, HKR95-219, NWGR9, and NWGR13 showed normal milled rice percentage and head rice recovery, long slender grains, intermediate GT, hard GC, and high AC.

References

- Cagampang GB, Perez CM, Juliano BO. 1973. A gel consistency test for eating quality of rice. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 24:1589–1594.
- Little RR, Hilder GB, Dawson EH. 1958. Differential effect of dilute alkali on 25 varieties of milled white rice. *Cereal Chem.* 35:111–126.
- Shen YZ. 1990. Genetical studies on amylose content of rice grain and modification of the determination method. *Sci. Agric. Sin.* 23(1):60–68. (in Chinese).
- Swain BR, Nagaraju M. 1997. Modified method for determination of amylose content using a single rice kernel. *Int. Rice Res. Notes* 22(1):48.
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Performance of prototype rice lines from ideotype breeding

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Several new plant type (NPT) rice breeding lines for the irrigated ecosystem have been developed at JNAU from crosses IR47705-AC5/ChIR87-3-1//Kranti (the 57K series), IR47705-AC5/IR32307-75-1-3-1//Kranti (the 63K series), and IR47705-AC5/IR28211-45-1-1-2//Kranti (the 72K series). These were based on a basic ideotype of rice (Janoria 1989).

We evaluated 16 NPT lines with three checks—MW10, IR36, and Kranti—during the 1996-97 dry (December-May) and wet (June-November) seasons at RARS. The two field experiments were laid out in a randomized block design with three replications, 6 × 1.2-m net plot size, and 20 × 20-cm spacing, and with 100-60-40 kg NPK ha⁻¹.

Five plants were randomly sampled per plot for plant height, panicle number

plant⁻¹, and grain number panicle⁻¹. Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) was estimated from net plots of 7.2 m² and days to maturity and 1,000-grain weight on a plot basis.

The top-yielding NPT lines in the early and medium maturity groups—NPT63K-1-20 and NPT63K-12-51, respectively—significantly ($P = 0.05$) outyielded the respective checks (see table) in both seasons. NPT57K-3-6 (very early) had a yield similar to its check MW10 during the wet season. NPT lines generally had a much higher grain number panicle⁻¹, lower panicle number plant⁻¹, and greater plant height than the semidwarf checks in accordance with the ideotype design.

The top-yielding NPT line (NPT63K-12-51) was resistant to bacterial leaf blight (caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae*) and sheath blight (caused by

Rhizoctonia solani f. sp. *sasakii*), the two major constraints to yield in Madhya Pradesh under artificial inoculation.

The longer duration of experimental entries in the dry season was due to lower temperatures during December and January, which slowed seedling growth in the nursery. Hence, seedling age at transplanting was 50 d in the dry season compared with 21 d in the wet season. Similarly, higher photothermal regimes during the postplanting phase reduced plant height and increased yields in the dry season.

Reference

- Janoria MP. 1989. A basic plant ideotype for rice. *Int. Rice Res. Notes* 14:12–13.
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